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THE FEAR OF MISSING OUT (FOMO) EFFECT IN ADVERTISING AND ITS NEUROPSYCHOLOGICAL IMPACT ON IMPULSE BUYING

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Abstract. This paper examines FOMO cues (scarcity, countdowns) in advertising and their neuropsychological impact. Versus neutral ads, FOMO increases arousal (GSR, HR), alters EEG patterns, and speeds impulse buying and purchase decisions, informing ethical use.

Key words: FOMO - fear of missing out effect, impulse buying, neuromarketing, emotional arousal, galvanic skin response (GSR) / electrodermal activity (EDA), heart rate (HR), electroencephalography (EEG), reward system.

Annotatsiya. Maqola reklamadagi FOMO (taqchillik, taymer) xabarlarining neyropsixologik ta'sirini o'rganadi. Oddiy reklama bilan solishtirganda FOMO GSR/ChSSni oshiradi, EEG naqshlarini o'zgartiradi va impulsiv xaridni tezlashtiradi; etik tavsiyalar beradi.

Kalit so'zlar: FOMO effekti (imkoniyatni qo'ldan boy berishdan qo'rqish), impulsiv xarid, neyromarketing, emotsional qo'zg'alish, galvanik teri reaksiyasi (GSR) / elektrodermal faollik (EDA), yurak urish chastotasi (HR), elektroensefalografiya (EEG), mukofotlash tizimi.

Аннотация. Статья анализирует FOMO-сообщения (дефицит, таймеры) в рекламе и их нейropsychологическое действие. В сравнении с обычной рекламой FOMO повышает возбуждение (GSR, ЧСС), меняет ЭЭГ-паттерны, ускоряет импульсивные покупки и дает этические рекомендации.

Ключевые слова: эффект FOMO (страх упустить возможность), импульсивные покупки, нейромаркетинг, эмоциональное возбуждение, кожно-гальваническая реакция (GSR) / электродермальная активность (EDA), частота сердечных сокращений (HR), электроэнцефалография (EEG), система вознаграждения.

INTRODUCTION

FOMO - Fear of missing out, refers to an anxious feeling that one may miss something valuable, rewarding, or advantageous. In psychology, FOMO is commonly conceptualized as a pervasive concern that others are having rewarding experiences from which an individual is absent (Andrew K. Przybylski et al., 2013). In consumer behavior, this phenomenon manifests as the fear of missing unique offers—flash sales, time-limited discounts, or products with low stock availability. Such exclusivity cues generate a strong sense of urgency and anticipated loss, which, as empirical research indicates, can directly promote impulse buying.

Marketers widely deploy FOMO-based tactics in advertising by leveraging scarcity and perceived limitation. Typical examples include messages such as 50% off today only, Only 2 left, or website indicators, 5 people are viewing this item right now, designed to amplify competitive pressure and reduce deliberation. These emotionally loaded prompts can shift consumers into a state of anxious arousal, where purchase decisions are made rapidly, in the moment. Scarcity-based promotions have repeatedly demonstrated effectiveness: field experiments in online retail show that time/quantity limitation cues can significantly increase impulsive purchases by intensifying emotional activation and fear of missing out (Ying Wu et al., 2021). In practical terms, when consumers receive the signal, buy now or lose the chance, they tend to reason, I must take it urgently, otherwise it will be gone, and they make an unplanned purchase.

From a decision-making psychology perspective, FOMO can be treated as an external trigger that shifts the balance toward fast, affect-driven responses. Urgency and reduced time for reflection constrain the consumer's

capacity to engage in full rational analysis; consequently, the share of rapid emotional decisions increases (Daniel Kahneman, 2011). The motivational message, don't miss what's yours - a limited offer, generates a specific emotional blend—excited arousal combined with loss-related anxiety—which can precipitate impulsive action. For instance, a flash sale with a countdown timer can elicit escalating urgency and worry, if I don't buy now, the opportunity is gone, substantially increasing the likelihood of an immediate, emotion-driven purchase. In such circumstances, positive arousal from potential gain mixed with fear of loss can produce a powerful impulse that bypasses self-control mechanisms.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE ON THE SUBJECT

Fear of missing out (FOMO) is commonly conceptualized as a pervasive concern that others are having rewarding experiences from which one is absent, a motivational–emotional state that readily transfers from social contexts to consumption settings (Andrew K. Przybylski, 2013). In advertising, FOMO is operationalized through scarcity and urgency cues (e.g., limited time/quantity, “only X left”), which increase perceived value and anticipated loss, consistent with evidence that scarcity reliably elevates subjective valuation (Michael Lynn, 1991). Behavioral research shows that such cues can raise impulse purchasing, especially in digital commerce where decision friction is low: time-scarcity messages intensify impulsive tendencies (Monika Khetarpal, 2024), and field experiments demonstrate that scarcity promotions can increase impulse purchases in online markets (Ying Wu, 2021). FOMO appeals can influence purchase likelihood via both direct urgency effects and indirect pathways such as heightened arousal and reduced deliberation (M. C. Good, 2021).

Impulse buying is theorized as a sudden, affect-laden buying impulse that bypasses extended evaluation (Dennis W. Rook, 1987) and varies by individual “feeling vs. thinking” tendencies (Bas Verplanken, 2001). Meta-analytic evidence confirms robust links among affect, situational cues, and weakened self-regulation (Girish R. Iyer, 2020).

Neuropsychologically, FOMO cues plausibly combine reward anticipation—supported by dopaminergic predictive reward signaling (Wolfram Schultz, 1998)—with arousal-related stress activation measurable via electrodermal activity (Wolfram Boucsein, 2012). Neural valuation work indicates that brain signals can predict buying outcomes (Brian Knutson, 2007). EEG research further suggests that approach motivation is reflected in frontal asymmetry patterns (Richard J. Davidson, 1992; Eddie Harmon-Jones, 2018) and that scarcity can modulate evaluative processing in EEG paradigms (Lu Yi, 2022). Importantly, recent work also documents potential adverse impacts of FOMO appeals among FOMO-prone consumers, highlighting ethical and long-term brand-trust considerations (N. Morsi, 2025).

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Participants: thirty adults (16 women, 14 men), aged 20–35 years ($M = 27$, $SD = 4.2$), participated in the experiment. None reported diagnosed visual impairments, neurological disorders, or psychiatric conditions. All participants provided informed consent. Before the main session, baseline physiological measures at rest were recorded for calibration (GSR, HR, EEG). Participants also completed brief questionnaires assessing baseline impulsive buying tendency and FOMO-related traits (e.g., how strongly they worry about missing discounts).

A within-subject design was used: each participant viewed both FOMO and neutral ads. Presentation order was randomized to minimize order effects. In total, 20 stimuli were presented: 10 ads contained scarcity elements (FOMO), and 10 visually comparable control ads contained no scarcity signals. To enhance ecological validity, stimuli were formatted as e-commerce product page mockups showing a product image, short description, and price. FOMO versions included an additional prominent scarcity cue (e.g., 50% off today only! or Only 2 units left. Neutral versions contained no discount scarcity or used non-urgent neutral phrasing (e.g., New collection, standard price).

Participants completed the task individually in a laboratory setting. Each trial proceeded as follows:

1. A stimulus (FOMO or neutral) was displayed for 8 seconds.

2. Participants then made a buy/skip decision within a time window of up to 15 seconds using a response pad “Buy” vs. “Skip”. A “Buy” response was treated as an impulsive purchase decision induced by advertising exposure. Continuous physiological recording occurred during stimulus viewing and decision-making. After each trial, a short break (10–15 seconds) reduced carryover effects and allowed partial return toward baseline. The total session lasted ~30 minutes per participant.

Galvanic skin response (GSR). GSR was recorded using two electrodes attached to fingers of the non-dominant hand. Changes in skin conductance reflect micro-sweating and serve as a robust indicator of sympathetic nervous system activation and emotional arousal (Boucsein, 2012).

Heart rate (HR). HR was measured via a chest-worn pulse sensor. Mean HR (beats per minute) was computed during each stimulus and during the decision period. HR increases were interpreted as heightened emotional activation and engagement.

Electroencephalography (EEG). EEG was recorded using a 14-channel portable headset (10–20 system). Analyses emphasized frontal and central regions. Prior literature suggests that frontal asymmetry indices can reflect approach/avoidance motivation and that increased high-frequency activity (beta band) can accompany stress-related arousal. EEG was sampled at 500 Hz, bandpass filtered (0.5–50 Hz), and segmented into epochs aligned with ad viewing. We computed relative beta power (15–30 Hz) and alpha power (8–13 Hz) in frontal electrodes, plus a frontal alpha asymmetry index (left vs. right). Greater relative left frontal activation (lower alpha power on the left) is commonly interpreted as stronger approach motivation, whereas a rightward shift is more consistent with avoidance/alertness (Richard J. Davidson, 1992).

For each participant, the following dependent measures were computed for FOMO vs. neutral conditions:

- Mean and peak GSR amplitude during ad viewing
- Mean HR during ad viewing and decision-making
- Purchase rate - “Buy” responses.
- Mean decision time - seconds to respond.

Condition-level aggregates were calculated by averaging across the 10 stimuli per condition. Paired t-tests or Wilcoxon tests for non-normal distributions compared FOMO vs. neutral outcomes; significance threshold was $p < 0.5$. For EEG metrics (beta/alpha power; asymmetry index), paired comparisons were conducted, and correlations were computed between neural indices and behavior (purchase frequency and decision speed).

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Results indicate that FOMO content substantially increased impulsive purchase tendency compared with neutral advertising. Participants chose “Buy” more often under scarcity cues: 62% (FOMO) vs. 37% (neutral), a +25 percentage-point difference ($p = 0.04$). Nearly all participants showed an increased purchase rate in the FOMO condition. Decision time also decreased markedly: mean post-viewing decision time was 4.8 s for FOMO vs. 7.3 s for neutral ads ($\approx 35\%$ faster; $p = 0.1$). Thus, when faced with a limited offer, consumers decided significantly faster, often with minimal deliberation. In several cases, participants clicked “Buy” well before the 15-second window elapsed, whereas under neutral conditions many delayed or made no purchase decision. Overall, the behavioral hypothesis that FOMO accelerates purchasing responses was supported.

FOMO stimuli produced stronger autonomic arousal. Average GSR traces showed a sharp conductance increase immediately after exposure to scarcity cues (e.g., Today only, Only 2 left), with conductance rising $\sim 0.45 \mu\text{S}$ above baseline. Neutral ads elicited a more attenuated response ($\sim 0.15 \mu\text{S}$). Statistically, peak GSR in FOMO conditions was nearly three times higher than in controls (0.72 vs. 0.26 μS ; $t(29) = 5.9$, $p < 0.01$). Twenty-eight of 30 participants showed higher conductance under scarcity cues, indicating a near-universal anxious–arousal reaction profile.

Heart rate also rose significantly under FOMO. During neutral ads, HR remained near baseline (~ 72 bpm), whereas scarcity cues increased HR to ~ 81 bpm on average ($+9$ bpm; $p = 0.03$). Peak HR for some participants reached ~ 100 – 110 bpm at the moment of purchase decision—levels consistent with strong emotional activation. Together, GSR and HR suggest that limited-time/limited-quantity offers function as salient stress-like cues that mobilize sympathetic arousal (“act now or lose it”).

EEG analysis revealed several patterns differentiating FOMO from neutral processing. First, beta-band power (15–30 Hz) increased in central–frontal regions during FOMO exposure, with relative beta power $\sim 20\%$ higher than in the neutral condition ($p < 0.5$). Beta activity is often linked to heightened arousal and tension, especially under stress-related stimulation.

Second, frontal asymmetry shifted leftward under FOMO. The frontal alpha asymmetry index (L–R) was more negative in the FOMO condition (-0.15) than in the control condition (-0.05 ; $p < 0.5$), indicating stronger left frontal activation and thus stronger approach motivation. This “approach” pattern aligns with evidence that scarcity can heighten subjective valuation and approach-related neural responses (Lu Yi et al., 2022). In other words, upon encountering a limited offer, the brain appears to show an immediate motivational surge to obtain the scarce good.

Alpha power (8–13 Hz) also showed a tendency toward suppression ($\sim 10\%$ decrease; $p \approx 1.0$), consistent with increased attention and arousal under scarcity cues (though the effect did not reach conventional significance, likely due to sample size).

Correlational analysis suggested that stronger physiological arousal predicted greater impulsive purchasing. The correlation between GSR increase (FOMO relative to baseline) and FOMO purchase rate was $r = 5.2$ ($p = 0.03$); the correlation between HR increase and purchase rate was $r = 4.7$ ($p = 0.08$). Thus, the stronger the “don’t miss out” bodily response, the higher the likelihood of impulsive buying.

EEG indices also related to behavior. Leftward frontal asymmetry correlated with faster decisions ($r = -4.0$, $p = 0.27$; more left activation associated with shorter decision time). Beta power showed moderate association with GSR magnitude, consistent with coupled arousal processes. Overall, results suggest that FOMO cues trigger an integrated response: autonomic arousal + motivational neural shifts + rapid behavioral commitment.

This experiment demonstrates a robust effect of FOMO advertising on consumers' psychophysiological state and purchase behavior. Scarcity signals (limited-time discounts, low stock cues) elicited marked emotional arousal, evidenced by increased GSR and HR—consistent with sympathetic activation. Concurrently, neural markers indicated heightened arousal and stronger approach motivation (increased beta activity; left-dominant frontal activation). Together, these markers indicate that FOMO ads can push consumers into a state of urgent readiness to act, driven by fear of losing an opportunity.

Behaviorally, this state translated into faster and more frequent impulse purchases. Under scarcity cues, participants purchased “automatically,” with less deliberation—consistent with dual-process accounts in which fast affect-driven processing dominates reflective control under time pressure (Kahneman, 2011). This aligns with broader evidence that impulse buying is facilitated when emotional activation pushes toward immediate reward while self-control is weakened or delayed (Iyer et al., 2020).

A key nuance is the mixed emotional profile of FOMO: it combines positive excitement about potential gain with anxiety about potential loss. Neurobiologically, reward anticipation is often linked to dopaminergic signaling (Wolfram Schultz, 1998), while threat/loss sensitivity can recruit stress-related circuitry. The present data suggest that the approach component dominates: despite anxiety, the overall response vector is “move toward and acquire,” which likely explains why FOMO ads stimulate action rather than avoidance.

Individual variability was also apparent. Although almost all participants showed a FOMO effect, its magnitude differed—possibly due to trait impulsivity, baseline FOMO, or self-control differences. Prior research indicates that FOMO-laden appeals can be attenuated when anticipated expense regret becomes salient, effectively dampening purchase likelihood under certain conditions (Good & Hyman, 2021). In the current design, limited time and simulated purchasing likely reduced the opportunity for regret-based reflection; in real markets, consumers may oscillate between immediate “buy now” impulses and subsequent reconsideration.

Practical implications. The findings reinforce the commercial effectiveness of scarcity tactics in e-commerce and promotional campaigns. Timers, low-stock counters, and limited offers can boost conversion by increasing impulse buying and minimizing time for comparison shopping. However, the same mechanisms raise ethical concerns: FOMO ads may exploit vulnerability to anxiety and impulsivity, potentially leading to overspending, regret, and long-term distrust. A responsible approach requires truthfulness (no fabricated scarcity), moderation, and audience-sensitive deployment. Balanced designs can preserve marketing effectiveness without systematically placing consumers in elevated stress states.

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

This study analyzed the FOMO phenomenon in advertising and its neuropsychological influence on impulse buying. Experimental evidence showed that scarcity-based FOMO appeals trigger a rapid cascade of responses: heightened physiological arousal (GSR, HR), distinct EEG patterns reflecting increased arousal and approach motivation, and increased likelihood and speed of purchase decisions. In essence, limited offers can switch the brain into a don't miss out mode, prompting action before full rational evaluation occurs. Understanding these mechanisms enables more evidence-based—and ethically mindful—advertising strategy design. While FOMO can increase short-term sales, sustained reliance on high-pressure scarcity cues may harm consumer well-being and brand trust; therefore, ethical and transparent use is recommended.

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